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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF HOLLOW
MICROSPHERES OF CLARITHROMYCIN FOR
GASTROINTESTINAL INFECTION****Thirumanikandan M^{1,2}, Karthik T^{1,2}, Rathish Ramankutty^{1,2*}**

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Abstract:

Gastrointestinal infections caused by pathogens such as Helicobacter pylori, Escherichia coli, and Salmonella present significant health challenges, often requiring prolonged antibiotic therapy. However, conventional oral treatments suffer from issues like poor bioavailability, limited drug concentration at the infection site, and frequent dosing, leading to suboptimal therapeutic outcomes. This study explores the development of hollow microspheres as a novel gastro-retentive drug delivery system (GRDDS) for clarithromycin, a widely used antibiotic. The aim was to enhance the drug's bioavailability and reduce dosing frequency. Hollow microspheres of clarithromycin were prepared using the emulsion solvent evaporation method with polymers such as Ethyl Cellulose, HPMC K4, and Eudragit S. The prepared microspheres were evaluated for drug encapsulation efficiency, particle size, surface morphology, buoyancy, and drug release profile. The results showed that the microspheres had a good buoyancy with floating lag times ranging from 50 to 80 seconds and total floating times exceeding 8 hours. The in vitro drug release followed zero-order kinetics, with formulation F5 (containing Ethyl Cellulose, HPMC K4, and Eudragit S) achieving 98.64% drug release over 10 hours. The optimized formulation demonstrated stability over a three-month period under accelerated conditions. The hollow microspheres significantly improved the bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy of clarithromycin, offering a promising solution to the limitations of conventional oral antibiotic therapies for gastrointestinal infections.

Keywords: *Hollow Microspheres, Clarithromycin, Gastro-retentive Drug Delivery System (GRDDS), Emulsion Solvent Evaporation, Drug Encapsulation, Sustained Release, Bioavailability, In-vitro Release, Floating Tablets, Kinetics.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Gastrointestinal infections are a significant global health problem, leading to substantial morbidity and mortality worldwide. These infections are typically caused by pathogens such as *Helicobacter pylori*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, and *Campylobacter jejuni*, which are often treated using antibiotics. However, conventional oral antibiotic therapies often face challenges, including poor drug absorption, low drug concentrations at the infection site, and the necessity for frequent dosing, resulting in suboptimal therapeutic outcomes and increasing the risk of antibiotic resistance (1).

The development of controlled and sustained drug delivery systems has become a critical area of research in order to overcome these limitations. Among the various strategies, gastro-retentive drug delivery systems (GRDDS) have emerged as a promising approach for enhancing the bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy of drugs used to treat gastrointestinal infections (2). These systems work by prolonging the residence time of drugs in the stomach, ensuring sustained drug release, and maintaining therapeutic drug concentrations over extended periods (3). Specifically, hollow microspheres, which are a subclass of GRDDS, have been shown to improve the controlled release of drugs and reduce dosing frequency (1).

Clarithromycin, a macrolide antibiotic, is frequently used to treat gastrointestinal infections, particularly those caused by *Helicobacter pylori*, which is responsible for peptic ulcers and gastric cancers (4). Despite its efficacy, clarithromycin suffers from poor oral bioavailability due to its low solubility and absorption in the gastrointestinal tract (5). To address these challenges, the use of hollow microspheres for the sustained release of clarithromycin has been explored, as these systems can enhance its bioavailability, prolong its action, and reduce the frequency of administration (6).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Clarithromycin, the drug of interest, was procured from Fourrts India Pvt Ltd. Polymers used for the formulation of hollow microspheres included Ethyl Cellulose (Oxford Labfine Chem, H.P.), HPMC K4 (Oxford Labfine Chem, H.P.), and Eudragit S (Ottokemi Pvt Ltd). Other chemicals such as dichloromethane, ethanol, and Tween 80 were used as solvents and emulsifying agents (6). All materials used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Hollow Microspheres

The hollow microspheres were prepared using the emulsion solvent evaporation method, which has been widely adopted for the development of gastro-retentive drug delivery systems (7). Briefly, the required amount of Ethyl Cellulose, HPMC K4, and Eudragit S were dissolved in a mixture of ethanol and dichloromethane. Clarithromycin was then added to the polymer solution, and the resulting solution was emulsified in 200 mL of aqueous Tween 80 solution. The emulsion was stirred at 1200 rpm for 4 hours, followed by drying at 40°C to form hollow microspheres (8).

Drug-Polymer Compatibility Studies

Compatibility studies between clarithromycin and the polymers used for microsphere formulation were conducted using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). FTIR spectra were recorded for the pure drug, polymers, and their physical mixtures to identify any potential interactions (9). DSC analysis was performed to study the thermal behavior of the drug and polymers, ensuring no significant thermal degradation occurred during the formulation process (10).

Evaluation of Hollow Microspheres

The hollow microspheres were characterized by various physicochemical parameters. The percentage yield of the microspheres was calculated after drying, and drug content and encapsulation efficiency were determined using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (11). Particle size distribution was measured using a laser diffraction particle size analyzer, and the surface morphology was observed using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (12).

The buoyancy of the microspheres was evaluated by determining the floating lag time (FLT) and total floating time (TFT) in 0.1N hydrochloric acid at 37°C (Arora et al., 2005). In-vitro drug release studies were conducted using a USP dissolution apparatus (USP-2, Paddle method) with 900 mL of 0.1 N hydrochloric acid as the dissolution medium at 37°C ± 0.5°C. The drug release data were analyzed for kinetic models including zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

STANDARD CURVE OF CLARITHROMYCIN PURE DRUG

Calibration curve of Clarithromycin was determined by plotting absorbance (nm) versus concentration (µg/ml) at 276 nm. The results obtained are as follows.

Table -1: Standard curve of Clarithromycin

S.NO	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (nm)
1	0	0
2	2	0.187
3	4	0.421
4	6	0.611
5	8	0.781
6	10	0.980

The linear regression analysis was done on absorbance data points. A straight line generated to facilitate the calculation of amount of drug, the equation is as follows:

$Y = mx + c$ Where Y =absorbance, m =slope, x =concentration

Drug-polymer compatibility study:

FT-IR studies:

The FT-IR spectra of the pure drug, excipient and physical mixture of drug and excipient were recorded in between 400-4000 wave number (cm^{-1}). No peaks are observed which interfere with the main drug peaks. The following spectrum and table shows IR spectrum for drug and polymer and the wave number of

characteristic bands for the same. The IR Spectrum preview pictures are as follows:

Table 2: FT-IR Peaks of various components

Peak in pure drug (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group	Type of vibration	Peak in Physical mixture
3533.35	Amine (N-H)	Stretch (medium)	3269.12
1708.81	Ketone (C=O)	Stretch (medium)	1718.46
1619.95	Alkene (C=C)	Stretch (Strong)	1684.52
1171.00	Carbonyl (C-O)	Stretch (Scissoring)	1276.79

Compatibility studies were performed using IR spectrophotometer. The IR spectrum of pure drug and physical mixture of drug and polymer were studied.

From the above results functional groups and type of vibrations are noted (Table no:5) In case of FT-IR study there was no disappearance or appearance of already existing peaks. Hence drugs were found to be compatible with excipients.

DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRY (DSC) STUDIES

The DSC thermogram of Clarithromycin showed endothermic transitions at 94.2°C and 237.2 °C due to the decomposition of Clarithromycin

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROGRAPH OF CLARITHROMYCIN MICROSPHERE

Figure 2: SEM photograph of formulation F 5

PERCENTAGE YIELD

Figure 3 : Percentage yield of Clarithromycin microsphere

DRUG CONTENT

Figure 4 : Drug content of Clarithromycin microsphere

ENCAPSULATION EFFICIENCY

Figure 5 : Encapsulation efficiency of Clarithromycin microsphere
PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION

Figure 6 : Particle size of Clarithromycin microsphere

Buoyancy / Floating Test

On immersion in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid solution P^H (1.2) at 37°C, the microsphere floated, and remained buoyant without disintegration. Table-10 shows the results of buoyancy study and shows buoyancy character of prepared tablet. The buoyancy lag time for F1-F9 was ranging from 50-80 secs. From the results it can be concluded that the batch containing both xanthan gum and guar gum showed good buoyancy lag time (BLT) and total floating time (TFT). Formulation F1 containing Ethyl cellulose, and HPMC K4 showed good BLT of 50 sec, while the formulation containing Ethyl cellulose and HPMC K4 alone showed highest BLT and TFT of greater than 8 hrs. This may be due to the amount of polymer and gas generating agent, which were kept constant in the present study.

Fig No 7: *In vitro* buoyancy study of Clarithromycin floating.

In vitro drug release study of formulated floating controlled release formulations

Fig No.8: *In vitro* drug release study

The formulated floating controlled release microspheres were then subjected to *in vitro* dissolution test for evaluating drug release from the formulation. The *in vitro* dissolution test was carried out in 900 ml of 0.1N hydrochloric acid in USP-II paddle type apparatus at 50 rpm and $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The results of dissolution study were depending on polymer concentration. Formulation containing xanthan gum alone released faster compared to that guar gum alone due to the less binding nature and controlled release property than that of guar gum. Formulation F5 containing Ethyl Cellulose (150 mg), HPMC K4 (50 mg) and Eudragit S (50mg) had given drug release 98.64% in 10 hrs. Then the formulations containing Ethyl Cellulose, HPMC K4 and Eudragit S were given better release profiles when compared with formulations containing xanthan gum alone and guar gum alone.

Table No.3: Kinetic Values Obtained from *F5* plot Formulation.

Formulation	Zero order R^2	First order R^2	Higuchi 2 R	Korsmeyer -Peppas R^2	n	Best fit model
<i>F5</i>	0.943	0.955	0.945	0.976	0.657	Peppas

In order to determine the mechanism of drug release from the formulations, the *In vitro* dissolution data was fitted to zero order, first order, Higuchi plot and Korsmeyer-Peppas plot was drawn and interpretation of release exponent value (n) was calculated, and results are shown in tables 22-23; figs 27-30. The results of R^2 for zero and first order were obtained as 0.943, 0.955. Based on that we will confirm the optimized formulation followed zero order release.

The drug release was diffusion controlled as the plot of optimized formulation *F5* was found 0.976 as regression coefficient in Higuchi plot. From Korsmeyer Peppas plot the release exponent value n was found as 0.657 and it was confirmed as the release of drug from the formulation was found as anomalous non-fickian transport of diffusion.

STABILITY STUDIES:

The optimized formulation was subjected to stability studies at $40^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\%$ for 3 months.

Storage condition at $40^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\%$

Dissolution data of percent cumulative drug release for formulation *F5*

The stability studies for optimized formulation *F5* were carried out based accelerated stability conditions & study of various parameters carried out at 0, 30, 60, 90 days of intervals and the results found satisfactorily and that reveals that the optimized formulation was stable under accelerated condition.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

The main objective of the present study was to develop floating formulation containing 250 mg of Clarithromycin for better therapy using natural polymers like Ethyl Cellulose, Eudragit S and HPMC K4. GRDDS improved the bioavailability and therapeutic efficiency of drug.

In the preformulation, FTIR, DSC study was carried out for pure drug Clarithromycin and excipients. It has not shown any interaction. Hence drugs were found to be compatible with excipients.

The prepared floating microsphere were evaluated for

various parameters like percentage yield, particle size, shape, encapsulation efficacy, buoyancy, and drug content. The buoyancy lag time of all the formulations were ranging from 50 sec to 80sec and its duration is >8 hrs.

Compared to all formulations *F5* showed the best buoyancy lag time, the buoyancy lag time for *F5* was found to be 70 sec. Total floating time of all formulations was found to be >8 hrs.

The prepared microsphere were then subjected to dissolution test for evaluating the *in vitro* drug release. The dissolution studies were carried out in 0.1N Hydrochloric acid in USP-32 apparatus at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The results of the dissolution studies indicated that the polymer concentration was having a substantial effect on the drug release from the microsphere. Formulation *F5* gave better controlled drug release and floating properties in comparison to the other formulations. This formulation took 70 sec to become buoyant.

The kinetic study was carried out for *F5* formulation which showed that the drug release followed zero order kinetics followed by non-fickian diffusion.

The stability studies were carried out for *F5* formulation at $45^\circ\text{C} / 175\% \text{RH}$ for 3 months. Data revealed that there was no considerable difference.

However, further *in vivo* studies can be carried out to support the results.

The overall results explained that the microsphere prepared by combination of ethyl cellulose, Eudragit S and HPMC K4 could be more effective on floating microsphere.

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